

**NAVIGATING THE SYSTEM: A QUALITATIVE EXPLORATION OF TEACHERS'
CHALLENGES IN SEEKING CAREER PROGRESSION OF DADIANGAS
SOUTH DISTRICT, DIVISION OF GENERAL SANTOS CITY**

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Navigating the System: A Qualitative Exploration of Teachers' Challenges in Seeking Career Progression of Dadiangas South District, Division of General Santos City

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Abstract

This study was conducted to explore the experiences of teachers in the Dadiangas South District, Division of General Santos City, focusing on the challenges they face in career progression and the influence of administrative policies and support systems. Using a qualitative, phenomenological approach, in-depth interviews were conducted with five teachers to gather insights into their career journeys. The analysis revealed six key themes: Promotion Challenges, highlighting delays and unclear criteria; Experience-Based Career Struggles, reflecting evolving challenges over time; Proactive Strategies for Advancement, emphasizing networking and professional development; Policy Barriers, pointing to favouritism and seniority-based promotions; Support System Gaps, indicating insufficient mentoring and training; and Recommendations for Improvement, advocating for clearer promotion policies and targeted professional development. The study concluded that while teachers exhibit resilience, systemic changes are needed to address barriers and enhance career progression, including transparent promotion practices, improved support systems, and more tailored professional growth opportunities.

Keywords: *career progression, phenomenological study, challenges*

Introduction

Teaching is often described as a noble profession because of the important role that teachers play in forming the minds of the next generations. Still, career development within the profession remains a very complicated reality. There are numerous problems teachers face when seeking career development, which, in turn, influences their job satisfaction and job retention. This paper looks at the lived experiences of educators in Dadiangas South District, Division of General Santos City, highlighting the difficulties they encounter when it comes to career advancement.

A career is not only an organizational function but also a process that people manage actively. Hall (2002) defines a career as a personal sequence of attitudes and behaviors associated with professional events throughout one's lifetime. This reflects a unique combination of guiding principles across fields such as education, society, politics, and spirituality (Phiper, 2003). Career success depends heavily on the opportunities provided within an organization. Professional development is stagnant in the absence of such opportunities, as various studies emphasize the critical link between career advancement and job satisfaction.

The lack of professional development opportunities is one of the main reasons for dissatisfaction among educators, which usually leads to high turnover rates. Borman and Dowling (2008) argue that even the most competent teachers leave their jobs when growth opportunities are limited. Similarly, McConnell III (2017) notes that career development is one of the most crucial factors that will determine teacher retention. For instance, Rhodes et al. (2004) established that professional development is among the top reasons that affect the satisfaction of teachers in the UK. These results highlight the need to handle career stagnation to retain brilliant teachers.

Professional development benefits both the individual and society. Gustafsson et al. (2018) posit that career advancement promotes both personal and professional satisfaction, which contributes to increased happiness and more avenues. However, Miller (2019) asserts that the constraints to development, as well as their wider social consequences, are rarely considered. Teachers often seek to advance their careers through management positions (Kalberg & Bezzina, 2018), yet structural constraints in career advancement routes are a pervasive problem.

External factors include social narratives, peer pressure, and income disparities that have an influence on teachers' motivation for professional growth (Mcmillan et al., 2016). Social media is one of those factors that form perceptions of success, which determine educators' choices and aspirations. As noted by Barros (2019) and Sadovets (2021), career stagnation often results in frustration and dissatisfaction. To this end, a strategic control plan and interventions that help teachers cope with barriers to advancement are crucial.

Despite the difficulties, career advancement is still crucial for enhancing the professional and personal lives of teachers. Research shows that financial insecurity and stagnant career ladders are among the reasons why educators face difficulties (Tantawy, 2020; Kaiser & Menkhoff, 2020). For instance, most teachers in the rank of Teacher I are burdened with loans and lack opportunities for advancement. This study hopes to fill in the gap by focusing on teachers' experiences within Dadiangas South District, providing some insight into what hinders teachers' progression and finding solutions that could help resolve career stagnation.

Research Questions

The study aimed to explore the lived experiences of PWD public teachers in South Cotabato, Philippines. Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What are the key challenges faced by teachers in the Dadiangas South District when navigating the career progression system in the Division of General Santos City?
2. In what ways do administrative policies and practices influence the career advancement opportunities for teachers in the Dadiangas South District?
3. How do teachers perceive the support systems available for career progression in the Dadiangas South District, and what improvements do they suggest?

Literature Review

The Career Progression of a Teacher

Minello et al. (2021) focus on the teachers who identified as academic mothers and their level of pursuit of professional development activities. Interviews were the main technique of data gathering and analysis used in the research. The findings demonstrated that academic moms' priorities shifted in tandem with the pandemic's effects on many facets of life, which negatively impacted their participation in activities aimed at advancing their careers. In order to preserve education during the pandemic, teachers allocated more time to concentrate on their teaching responsibilities because the new learning style requires a lot of time to prepare for the printed modules and online learning activities and assignments.

In addition to the stress and challenges brought about by the new mode of instruction (Wong et al., 2021), obstacles to using online resources such as the internet (Nocco et al., 2021), and the demands of motherhood (Staniscuaski et al., 2020), educators also had a shortage of time, which caused them to postpone assignments, especially research, that were critical to their professional growth. The study also made clear that professors without children or who were not parents were more successful in developing their professions, and that academic mothers felt the most disadvantaged, which demotivated them (Cabello, 2022). Given this, the study recommended that the education sector focus on these teachers and offer them more opportunities by allocating sufficient funding for professional development.

No matter what our line of work, we always take a chance on the future while pursuing our passion (Cabello et al., 2022). This work draws on prior research that shows how a person's profession choice might impact their overall development within their field (Bennett & Hennekem, 2018). An open-ended exam was used to reflect their choice of career (Roberts & Lyons, 2020). Additionally, an open-ended survey allows educators to describe how they would react in light of their own engagement as this study clarifies the lived experiences. The theoretical framework of self-composition suggests in the analysis section that it will help them comprehend and define their lived experiences (Caselli et al., 2020). Advancement in one's career is essential for any job or career. Social standing rises as a result, and job satisfaction is high. This increases productivity and engagement in particular. To achieve a high standard of performance in their sector, teachers must be capable of teaching and learning (Kost et al., 2020).

To meet high standards of instruction, teachers must design lesson plans that let students study on their own (Poitras et al., 2019). The purpose of this paper is to assist educators in acquiring knowledge that will enable them to make adjustments to their practice over time. Participants were randomized at random to either of the two stable or current browser versions, according to Choi et al. (2020). The structural equation design indicates that teachers anchored the dynamic kind of browser slightly longer during the plenary learning session. However, in terms of efficacy, educators do a respectable job of assisting students in comprehending the subject matter, but they are unable to demonstrate to pupils who are functioning in a static condition on the topic scheme task (Chen et al. 2018).

Methodology

Research Design

Transcendental Phenomenological Method was utilized as a research design to derive the essence of such experiences, in this case that of teachers, in terms of career progression. This study would be best suited for this approach because it would be dealing with the actual lived experiences of an individual intuitively.

Participants

The study's informants are five teachers. The researcher decisively selected the participants using the following inclusion standards: (a) Participants should be a teacher from Dadiangas South District, Division of General Santos City. (b) Participants are classroom advisers or subject teachers. (c). Participants are either pursuing post graduate studies or have been stagnant for quite sometimes. (d) The participants should in their current position for more than 5 years.

Instrument

Guide questions were employed by the researcher in analysing teachers' dilemmas with regard to their career advancements within the Dadiangas South District in General Santos Division. Participants in the interviews provided their responses using the guide questions; these responses were audio and voice-recorded to ensure that the participants' own voices accurately enlightened the recorder. Both the researcher and the participants played significant roles, with the researcher ensuring that participants' rights were respected and their perspectives were considered.

Names and other personal details of the participants were not included in any material from the research. The records from the study were kept confidential, and no identifying details were shared. All personal data were securely destroyed once the study was completed. This method ensured the privacy of the participants and adhered to ethical standards for research.

Procedure

To complete this study, the researchers followed a step by the step process to gathering the data needed. Before data collection, the researcher requested permission from the school principal of Dadiangas South District, Division of General Santos City. After receiving the principal's assent, the researcher sent a formal permission letter to the participants. This letter communicated their rights: the freedom to withdraw anytime without any adverse consequences and that all data gathered would be kept confidential.

A consent form was signed by each participant before accepting to participate in the study. The researcher provided a clear verbal explanation of the consent form, the aim of the research, the data gathering process, and how their responses were going to be used. This ensured participants fully understood their involvement and rights.

To ensure data integrity, the researcher took special care in transcribing and analyzing the data. All interviews were accurately transcribed, maintaining participants' original responses with respect to the ethical standards of research. Additionally, participants had the opportunity to review the transcripts and research findings for accuracy, thus further ensuring authenticity and trustworthiness.

All the data collected were obtained with the participants' explicit consent. The researcher assured the participants of confidentiality and that their responses would be anonymous throughout the study. This included omitting any identifying information in the final research report.

Data Analysis

The researchers transcribed and translated the informants' conversations to ensure the accuracy and clarity of the acquired data. The study began by removing the researchers' subjectivity, leaving any assumptions or prejudices behind in order to examine the issue objectively. Data analysis was carried out in a methodical manner, beginning with horizontalization, which involved identifying all key phrases and removing extraneous or repeated words, leaving just the essential horizons. Thematic clustering was next performed, which involved grouping data into units of meaning and creating clustered themes to reflect participants' experiences. The "what" and "how" of the phenomena were written in the third person to represent the group's collective narratives. The researchers transcribed and translated the informants' conversations to ensure the accuracy and clarity of the obtained data.

Ethical Considerations

This study followed ethical requirements. Respondents freely participated. Care was taken to assure their safety and well-being: being, and that they had no physical, mental, social, or emotional impairment. There was always respect for the school head. Participants include stakeholders. The privacy of the information obtained.

Results and Discussion

The analysis revealed six (6) relevant themes, synthesized through initial themes, clustered themes, and formulated meanings.

These themes reflect the multifaceted nature of teachers' experiences in career progression, the influence of administrative policies, and the support systems available to them. The themes identified were: Promotion Challenges, Experience-Based Career Struggles, Proactive Strategies for Advancement, Policy Barriers, Support System Gaps, and Recommendations for Improvement.

Relevant Theme 1: Promotion Challenges

The theme of Promotion Challenges highlights the difficulties teachers face when navigating the promotion process within the Division of General Santos City. Despite their dedication and hard work, teachers often experience long waiting periods, unclear promotion guidelines, and perceived Favouritism, which hinder their career advancement.

Most participants shared that they endured lengthy waiting times, with delays ranging from 4 to 8 years before achieving promotion. Participant 1 explained, "I waited 5 years for my promotion. It required passing an exam, interviews, and preparing documents." Similarly, Participant 2 revealed, "I had to wait for 6 years, and the process was exhausting. I had to keep rechecking my documents and ensure I met all requirements, which were not clearly communicated."

Unclear criteria for promotion were also a major concern. Participant 3 expressed confusion, saying, "I had no idea about the exact requirements until I was already part of the process. They seemed to change depending on who was involved in decision-making." Participant 4 highlighted issues of Favouritism, noting, "I faced challenges due to Favouritism in the selection process. Sometimes, it felt like the decision was not based on performance or qualifications but on personal relationships."

Additionally, rigid and procedural inefficiencies were frustrating for many. Participant 5 stated, "The process was very rigid. Even if you met all the requirements, you still had to wait for someone to retire or for a position to open up, which could take years." These collective experiences underscore the systemic barriers in the promotion process, including inefficiencies, lack of transparency, and

perceived inequities, leaving teachers feeling demotivated and undervalued.

The study by Pagayanan (2021) identified that teachers are usually subjected to long delays in promotions, whereby some have spent more than a decade in the same position. They noted that procedural inefficiencies, such as the lack of structured timelines and bottlenecks, significantly contribute to these delays, causing frustration and demotivation among teachers. Similarly, the study by Osman & Adanza (2023) investigated the lack of clear guidelines in the promotion process. They stated that most of the teachers do not know what they exactly need to be promoted because policies seem confusing and very arbitrary depending on who makes the decision. This obscurity undermines trust and morale in teaching. Second, Luy, C. & Diaz, R. (2022) noted that there is favoritism in promotion. Their findings revealed that the teachers believe personal relationships and connections outweigh qualifications or performance in promotions, which undermines meritocracy and discourages excellence. Lastly, Delos Reyes (2020) stated that inflexible promotion systems often force teachers to wait for positions to open up because of retirements or other vacancies. This inflexibility greatly prolongs the promotion cycle and restricts opportunities for career advancement, causing educators to feel stagnant and underappreciated. Taken together, these studies highlight systemic barriers in the promotion process that contribute to teacher dissatisfaction.

Relevant Theme 2: Experience-Based Career Struggles

The theme of Experience-Based Career Struggles encompasses how the challenges teachers face evolve over time, shifting from early-stage struggles such as classroom management to long-term obstacles related to career stagnation and lack of opportunities for growth.

Two clustered themes emerged within this relevant theme: Early Career Adjustments and Mid-Career Stagnation. These were derived from initial themes such as "Adapting to the teaching environment" and "Struggling with limited career advancement opportunities."

Participants reported varied experiences that highlight how career challenges evolve throughout their teaching journey. Participant 1 described how, as a new teacher, they initially faced difficulties with preparing lesson plans and meeting the expectations of students, saying, "I found it overwhelming to manage lesson planning and classroom discipline during my first year of teaching." Similarly, Participant 2 shared, "As a new teacher, I struggled with classroom management," pointing out that adapting to the teaching environment and managing student behaviour was a steep learning curve. According to Ingersoll and Strong (2011), new teachers face many difficulties. It indicates that beginning teachers experience a problem in classroom management and lesson planning. The research reveals that if support and mentoring are given, novice teachers adjust to the teaching environment better and, therefore, stress levels reduce early in the career. In connection, the research by Day and Gu (2010) discusses how teachers' career challenges change over time. They suggest that early-career teachers often have problems associated with classroom discipline and instructional planning, while mid-career teachers face career stagnation due to fewer opportunities for professional development and promotions. Their work suggests that teacher motivation and job satisfaction are important in maintaining teachers' motivation for their profession.

Over time, the challenges shifted from classroom adjustments to career stagnation. Participant 3 noted, "I eventually adjusted to teaching, but I began to feel stuck when I realized that promotion opportunities were limited, and professional growth felt out of reach." This sentiment was echoed by Participant 4, who said, "After gaining experience, I realized that the lack of career advancement pathways became the main hurdle in my professional growth." Teachers expressed frustration with limited opportunities to advance their careers or develop new skills. Participant 5 reflected on this evolution, saying, "Early on, I lacked confidence; now, my challenge is finding opportunities to up skill and take on leadership roles." Likewise, this evolution of challenges is also supported by Kraft and Papay (2014), who indicated that teacher effectiveness plateaus when there are not meaningful opportunities for professional learning and career advancement. They stress that school systems must provide continuous opportunities for skill development to address the feelings of stagnation among the experienced teachers.

Relevant Theme 3: Proactive Strategies for Advancement

The theme of Proactive Strategies for Advancement reflects the actions teachers take to overcome career challenges, such as seeking mentorship, attending training, and documenting their achievements.

Two clustered themes emerged within this relevant theme: Networking and Professional Development and Achievement Tracking. These were derived from initial themes such as "Building relationships with administrators" and "Documenting teaching successes."

Teachers employed various strategies to address career advancement challenges, showcasing their proactive efforts in navigating systemic barriers. Participant 1 highlighted the importance of mentorship, stating, "I sought guidance from mentors and focused on improving my teaching portfolio." Similarly, Participant 2 shared, "I made sure to attend as many training sessions as possible and implemented what I learned in my classroom to demonstrate my skills." Networking also emerged as a key strategy, with Participant 3 noting, "I networked with colleagues to stay updated on policies and prepared for exams ahead of time."

The study by Hobson and Malderez (2013) highlights the critical role that mentorship plays in the professional development of teachers. They highlighted that effective mentoring connects theoretical knowledge to practical application and supports both professional and personal development. This aligns with Participant 1's statement about seeking guidance from mentors to improve their teaching portfolio. The study by Darling-Hammond, Hyler, and Gardner (2017) highlights the need to participate in professional development activities. They indicated that participation in workshops and training sessions enhances teachers' instructional skills and propels their

career advancement. This supports Participant 2's strategy of attending training sessions and applying the knowledge in the classroom. Lave and Wenger (1991) have explored the advantages of professional networking in learning communities. They noted that networking leads to collegial interactions, which guide and encourage. This is similar to what Participant 3 did: network with colleagues to be updated and ready.

Additionally, teachers emphasized documenting their accomplishments as a vital approach. Participant 4 explained, "I kept a record of all my achievements and used them as evidence during evaluations and promotion interviews." Meanwhile, Participant 5 stated, "I attended workshops and conferences, and I made it a habit to summarize the new knowledge I gained in a portfolio to show my growth." These efforts underline a common understanding among participants that taking the initiative to seek opportunities, build professional relationships, and document successes is essential for overcoming the limitations of existing systems and achieving career progression. The study by Kraft, Marinell, and Shen-Wei Yee (2016) shows that recording professional success is essential for career advancement. The authors noted that if accomplishments are well documented, then it becomes easier to conduct systematic and regular reviews when reviewing for promotions. This resonates with the practices of Participants 4 and 5, who keep a portfolio of their success and new knowledge acquired.

Relevant Theme 4: Policy Barriers

The theme of Policy Barriers sheds light on the restrictive and inequitable nature of administrative policies that obstruct teachers' career progression in the Division of General Santos City. Participants unanimously expressed their frustrations with a system that, in their view, prioritizes rigid, seniority-based criteria and personal relationships over actual performance and merit. These policies have created a culture of dissatisfaction, discouragement, and inequity among teachers.

Participant 4 shared a particularly disheartening perspective, stating, "Administrative decisions often depend on personal relationships rather than clear policies." This sentiment highlights the perceived favouritism that undermines confidence in the system. Participant 3 echoed this concern, adding, "Policies focus on paperwork and compliance, which discourages many teachers." This statement reflects how excessive bureaucratic requirements detract from meaningful evaluation metrics, leaving teachers feeling that their hard work and accomplishments are overlooked in favour of procedural formalities.

The lack of transparency in promotion criteria further aggravates the situation. Participant 1 explained, "The promotion process is confusing because there are no clear criteria. Sometimes, it feels like the system isn't based on merit but on who you know." This lack of clarity leads to a perception of unfairness, making teachers uncertain about what is required to advance their careers. This is compounded by Participant 2, who remarked, "It's frustrating to see others being promoted because of connections while those of us who work hard are overlooked." This comment underscores the demoralizing effect of Favouritism on teachers who diligently perform their duties yet feel excluded from opportunities for advancement.

In addition to Favouritism, the seniority-based promotion system also draws criticism. Participant 5 observed, "The seniority-based approach doesn't always reflect the actual performance of teachers. It feels like experience is prioritized over capability or achievements." While seniority can be a valuable consideration, participants expressed that it should not be the sole determinant of career progression. This rigid approach often prevents capable and high-performing teachers from advancing in their careers, stifling motivation and innovation within the system.

Moreover, participants emphasized how these policy barriers create an environment of frustration and stagnation. Teachers feel stuck in their positions, unable to achieve professional growth despite their dedication and qualifications. The combination of unclear promotion guidelines, excessive bureaucracy, Favouritism, and an overreliance on seniority erodes trust in the system and diminishes teachers' morale. As Participant 3 poignantly noted, "Policies like these discourage many teachers."

Favoritism is defined as a widespread problem, according to Erdem (2010), as deviations from justice in favor of particular individuals or groups. This is consistent with the participants' concerns about overbureaucratic paperwork and compliance, which undermine meaningful assessments and create a sense that the efforts of teachers are ignored in favor of procedural formalities. Nadler and Schulman (2006) argue that favoritism arises from subjective factors such as personal relationships or group membership, rather than performance, and this significantly undermines the perceived fairness of institutional decisions. Another concern raised by the participants was the lack of transparency regarding promotion criteria. This is in accordance with Oren's (2007) argument that favoritism is based on kinship or friendship relations rather than merit, making teachers feel unfairly treated. Further criticism of the system was based on the seniority-based promotion which often failed to consider teachers' competencies in promotion. Such rigid systems, where performance and even success are not accounted for, suffocate innovation and motivation within the school workforce. In fact, such systems favoring personal or political connections may worsen the case against organizational effectiveness and morale, notes Akozer (2013). Overall, this confluence of favoritism, bureaucratic inefficiencies, lack of transparency in promotion criteria, and an over-reliance on seniority results in a demoralizing and stagnant work environment for teachers, leaving them feeling undervalued and uncertain about their career prospects.

Relevant Theme 5: Support System Gaps

The theme of Support System Gaps reflects insufficiencies in current support systems for career progression, particularly in terms of

mentoring, training, and career development opportunities. Despite the existence of some formal programs aimed at fostering teacher development, many teachers reported that these offerings were inadequate or misaligned with their actual professional needs.

Two clustered themes emerged within this relevant theme: Insufficient Mentoring and Training and Lack of Tailored Support Programs. These were derived from initial themes such as "Limited training opportunities" and "Training programs not aligned with individual career goals."

Participants expressed a common dissatisfaction with the current support structures available to them. Participant 3 explained, "Professional development is offered, but the quality and frequencies are insufficient," emphasizing that while training programs existed, they did not occur regularly enough to foster continuous development. She added, "The sessions are often too short and not deep enough to have a lasting impact on my practice." Similarly, Participant 4 noted, "Support systems don't address real-world challenges or long-term career planning." According to this participant, the current programs failed to focus on the practical aspects of teaching or to help teachers plan for sustained career growth. Participant 5 added, "While there are some workshops, most of them are general and not specifically tailored to the specific challenges we face in the classroom." This response illustrates the disconnection between available professional development opportunities and the actual needs of teachers on the ground.

Despite these frustrations, some teachers did mention positive experiences with mentoring programs. Participant 1 shared, "I have had good mentoring in the past, but it was limited to only a few sessions. I feel that mentorship should be on-going, especially in terms of helping teachers navigate their career paths." This response suggests that although mentoring was appreciated, its sporadic nature diminished its potential long-term impact. Participant 2 also acknowledged the benefits of mentorship, saying, "When I first started, I had a mentor who helped me adjust to the classroom, but there was no follow-up after that. I feel like continuous mentorship could have helped me improve more." Both of these insights reveal that while there is some mentoring in place, it is often short-term and not sustained over the course of a teacher's career.

Teachers were not satisfied with the professional development opportunities that are currently provided. They opined that there are training programs, but these are not very frequent or intense enough to be continuous. Darling-Hammond et al. (2017) also pointed out that many professional development programs do not help in bringing meaningful changes in teaching practices and students' outcomes. Their research highlights the fact that professional development needs to be sustained over time, collaborative, and responsive to the specific needs of teachers. Similarly, the concern that programs do not address real-world challenges or support long-term career growth suggests a gap in the ability of current programs to provide the necessary, sustained support. This is the view of Yun et al. (2007), who underscored the need for continuous, high-quality professional development relevant to the contexts of teachers' experiences in the classroom.

Although some respondents appreciated the mentoring programs, they also pointed out that such experiences were sometimes limited and brief. This means that there should be more extended mentorship in a teacher's career. As much as mentoring contributes to a reduced teacher attrition rate, studies such as those carried out by Ingersoll and Kralik (2004) have established the fact that it lacks depth as well as sufficient ongoing support from which any actual positive impacts in practice would benefit.

Relevant Theme 6: Recommendations for Improvement

The theme of Recommendations for Improvement reflects the teachers' suggestions for enhancing the support systems and promotion processes. Participants recommended creating clearer policies, offering more targeted training, and ensuring that support systems are more personalized to address individual teachers' needs and career goals. The suggestions revealed a common desire for a more structured, transparent, and equitable system that can effectively facilitate career progression within the district.

Two clustered themes emerged within this relevant theme: Enhanced Professional Development and Transparent Promotion Practices. These were derived from initial themes such as "Improving training programs" and "Creating clearer and more equitable promotion pathways."

Teachers provided valuable insights into how career progression systems could be improved. Participant 2 emphasized the need for more personalized and goal-oriented training, stating, "Offer training tailored to teachers' specific goals and create a clearer promotion pathway." This recommendation suggests that current professional development programs may not fully align with individual teachers' aspirations or areas of improvement, which can hinder their growth. By offering targeted training that addresses specific career goals, teachers would be better equipped to advance in their careers. Additionally, Participant 5 proposed, "Allocate more resources for training and create specific programs for aspiring leaders." This statement highlights the need for more resources dedicated to developing leadership skills among teachers. Such programs could help identify and nurture future leaders, ensuring that there is a pipeline of qualified individuals ready to take on higher roles within the educational system.

Further, Participant 1 echoed the importance of clarity in the promotion process, sharing, "Promotion pathways need to be transparent. Teachers should know exactly what is expected to advance." This statement underscores the current confusion and lack of transparency in the promotion process, where teachers are often unsure of the criteria or steps required to move forward. Participant 3 also reinforced this point, saying, "The process needs to be less about seniority and more about merit. We need to focus on teachers' actual performance and contributions." This indicates a widespread dissatisfaction with the seniority-based promotion system, which many teachers feel

does not adequately reflect their skills, achievements, or potential.

Moreover, Participant 4 suggested, "There should be a formal mentorship program that pairs experienced teachers with new ones to help guide their career development." This response highlights the importance of structured mentorship as part of the support system. Teachers often feel that mentorship is crucial in navigating career challenges, and a formal program could provide the guidance and support needed to foster professional growth.

The findings of the study are in agreement with the extant literature, which emphasizes that career progression of teachers is best enhanced through personalized professional development, transparent promotion pathways, and a strong mentorship system. Boyd et al. (2008) note that principals are instrumental in retaining teachers through recognition, support, and professional collaboration opportunities. They point out that good leadership inspires professional development, a fact shared by Participant 5's suggestion to provide additional resources for focused leadership development training. Such support, especially in the form of training for emerging leaders, would ensure that the future leaders are groomed and prepared to assume higher positions in the education sector.

Additionally, the researchers of Flores and Day (2006) discovered that in school settings where there is supportive, informative, and encouraging leadership, positive attitudes toward teaching prevail, extending retention in the profession. This finding suggests the usefulness of suggesting a formal mentorship program along with Participant 4, as they reflect the clear importance of mentorship in professional development and the facilitation of longevity. Support from leadership is very important in the early years of a teacher's career, since Ronfeldt and McQueen (2017) found that providing early support reduces the chances of leaving the profession within the first five years by as much as 58%. This aligns with Participant 4's call for structured mentorship that can guide novice teachers through the challenges of their careers.

McCann and Johannesen, in 2004, reported that the problems of novice teachers include students' attitude, relationship problems with colleagues, time management, and curriculum knowledge. School administrators can help to overcome these challenges by providing clear communication channels, feedback, and coaching as recommended by Brock and Grady in 1998, citing that novice teachers expect principals to communicate the criteria for effective teaching and provide regular feedback. This makes it important for clarity in the promotion process, as Participant 1 has indicated, emphasizing that the pathway of promotion should be transparent.

Finally, the studies suggest that principals can support novice teachers by creating collaborative environments, which includes offering opportunities for teachers to observe one another and engage in professional dialogue. Roberson and Roberson (2009) noted that such collaborative settings can significantly reduce the likelihood of teacher attrition, supporting Participant 3's recommendation to focus promotions on merit and actual performance rather than seniority.

Conclusions

This study focused on the problems and experiences of teachers in the Dadiangas South District, highlighting the struggles and perseverance of teachers in career progression. Key conclusions include:

Teachers face significant barriers in career advancement, such as long waiting times, unclear promotion criteria, and perceived favoritism. These issues hinder career growth despite teachers' commitment.

The career struggle has evolved with time. Initially, it focuses on classroom management issues, while later it changes to stagnation and a lack of professional development.

The proactive strategies in terms of mentorship and professional development will be helpful to overcome barriers as teachers take control of their growth in case of the absence of institutional support.

Administrative policies hinder career progression, with promotions often based on seniority or personal relationships, contributing to frustration and a desire for more transparent, merit-based processes.

Support systems are inadequate, with limited, infrequent, and poorly aligned training opportunities. Teachers call for more targeted, high-quality professional development.

Teachers call for systemic changes that include more transparent promotion processes, more resources to support professional growth, and career development programs.

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